

PEIERLS–NABARRO BARRIER IN THE SURFACE LAYER OF ALLOTROPIC MODIFICATIONS OF CARBON

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10609838>

Abstract

The purpose of this article is to determine the thickness of the surface layer of carbon materials and calculate the Peierls–Nabarro barrier in this layer. It is shown that for diamond the thickness of the surface layer is $R(I) = 0.58$ nm and contains only (2) monolayers. It is shown that at a graphite density of 1.75 g/cm³ in the longitudinal direction $R(I)_a = 1.17$ (4) nm, and in the transverse direction $R(I)_c = 3.19$ (4) nm. It was shown that for α -carbyne $R(I)_a = 38.6$ (43) nm and $R(I)_c = 196.7$ (128) nm, which is significantly more than 100 nm. It turned out that carbyne is the strongest of all known materials. For fullerenes, for C₆₀ $R(I) = 85.6$ (60) nm, for C₇₀ $R(I) = 93.4$ (64) nm. We compare the $R(I)$ monolayer with the Peierls–Nabarro barrier, which is equal to the force of interatomic interaction. We compared the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ to the length of nanocracks L_{nm} , which appears in any solid during the formation of its surface. In this case, the surface layer $R(I)$ is subjected to internal stresses due to relaxation or reconstruction of the surface. It is shown that the height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier is maximum: carbyne $\rightarrow$ C₇₀ $\rightarrow$ diamond. If we want to increase strength and strengthen the material, then we need to increase the height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier for moving dislocations (nanocracks) in the crystal structure. It has been shown that the height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier for graphite is 5 times less than for diamond. It is shown that the Peierls–Nabarro stress $\sigma(I) = 4.3$ GPa, which leads to warping of graphene. Also, the Stone-Wales defect can be considered as a dislocation dipole. The Peierls–Nabarro barrier is equal to $F(I) = 1.29 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N for α -carbyne, which is greater than that of diamond. This means dislocation inhibition for α -carbyne and means its strength. It has been shown that, in addition to carbyne, C₇₀ fullerene and diamond, most crystals, including steels, have Peierls–Nabarro barriers that do not exceed $1 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, so they are not as strong as diamond.

Keywords: Diamond, graphite, carbyne, fullerene, carbon, nanocrack, dislocation, strength.

Introduction

Carbon exists in several allotropic modifications and in various isomorphous states with very diverse physical properties [1-4]. There are three basic geometries for the carbon atom: tetrahedral, trigonal, and diagonal. The tetrahedral geometry of the carbon atom (sp^3 hybridization) corresponds to the allotropic modifications of carbon: diamond and lonsdaleite. The trigonal modification is formed by mixing one s - and two p -electron orbitals. The carbon atom has three equivalent $\sigma_{x,y}$ bonds located in the same plane at an angle of 120° to each other. The p_z orbital, which is not involved in hybridization and is located perpendicular to the

plane of σ bonds, is used to form a π bond with other atoms. It is this carbon geometry that is characteristic of graphite (sp^2 hybridization) [5]. Carbon with diagonal atomic geometry forms a special allotropic modification - carbyne (sp -hybridization), however, in the materials synthesized to date, the length of straight carbyne without bends and interchain bonds is less than a hundred atoms [6]. The work [7] depicts all known forms of existence of free carbon in the form of a triangle diagram (Fig. 1), at the vertices of which there are chemical compounds characterized by one type of hybridization of the carbon atom (sp , sp^2 or sp^3).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of allotropic modifications of carbon ([7]).

The phase diagram of Bundy carbon is shown in Fig. 2 [8].

Figure 2. Bundy phase diagram of carbon [8].

Schemes of the structure of various modifications of carbon are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Schemes of the structure of various modifications of carbon: carbine (a); diamond (b); graphite (c); lonsdaleite (g); fullerene – C_{60} (d); fullerene – C_{70} (e); amorphous carbon (f); carbon nanotube (i), (k).

Payerls -Nabarro model is one of the most effective tools used in the study of dislocations in materials [11]. This model uses both the distant field of elastic displacements of dislocation and the quantum description of the area of its nucleus on the surface of the generalized energy of defects (OED) of the styling, or γ -to-surface [12].

The purpose of this article is to determine the thickness of the surface layer of carbon materials and the calculation of the Payerls barrier - nabarro in this layer.

The thickness of the surface layer of carbon materials

In [11], the proposed model of the surface layer of atomic-bonded metals proposed. To determine the thickness of the surface layer of various compounds, the dimensional dependence of the melting temperature $T_m(r)$ was used:

$$T_m(r) = T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/r), \quad r \gg R(I), \quad (1)$$

$$T_m(r) = T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/R(I) + r), \quad R(0) \leq r \leq R(I).$$

Here, the first formula coincides with the formula R. Tolmen [12], where $R(I) = 2\delta$, δ is the parameter of Tolmen, which is not experimentally determined. The

second formula is determined in the area $0 < r < R(I)$ so that with $R = 0$ the first formula does not turn into infinity. The parameter $R(I)$ is associated with surface energy γ with a formula [11]:

$$R(I) = 2\gamma v / RT. \quad (2)$$

Here γ is the surface energy of a massive sample; v is the volume of one mole; R is a constant gas; T is the temperature. [13] shows that with an accuracy of 3% performed:

$$\gamma = 0,70 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m [\text{Äæî}^2], \quad (3)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the solid (K). The ratio is performed for all metals and for other crystalline compounds. With $T = T_m$ from (2) we get:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} v \quad (i). \quad (4)$$

Schematically this model is presented in Fig. 4a. Equation (4) shows that the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ is determined by one parameter - a molar (atomic) volume of the element ($v = m/\rho$, m - molar mass (kg/mol), ρ - density (kg/m³)), which periodically changes in accordance with the table D.I. Mendeleev (Fig. 4b).

Figure 4. Schematic image of the surface layer (a), periodic change in the atomic volume of elements (b)

From Fig. 4B carbon is at the beginning of the periodic table near Bor. Description Fig. 4a is given in detail in the work [11]. For accounting for anisotropy, the ratios were used [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} Pm3m, Z = 1, l_{100} &= 2R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\ Im3m, Z = 2, l_{100} &= R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\ Fm3m, Z = 4, l_{100} &= R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\ Fd3m, Z = 8, l_{100} &= R(I)/2, l_{110} = R(I)/\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In [15] we give the following ratios:

$$\begin{aligned} R(I) &= 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \dot{I} / \rho, \\ R(I)_{\delta=\dot{a}} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot \dot{\delta}(\dot{a})^3, \\ R(I)_{y=b} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot y(b)^3, \\ R(I)_{z=c} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot z(c)^3, \\ \gamma_{\dot{a}} &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_{\dot{a}} / R(I), \\ \gamma_b &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_b / R(I), \\ \gamma_c &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_{\dot{c}} / R(I). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Using equations (1) - (6), calculate the surface layer $R(I)$ for hydrocarbons.

Diamond

The structure of the diamond (Fig. 3b) belongs to the symmetry $Fd3m$. The lattice parameter $a = 0.357$ nm, melting temperature $T_m = 3973-4273$ K, density $\rho = 3.47-3.55$ (g/cm³), molar mass $M = 12.01$ (g/mol) [1].

Table 1.

The parameters of the structure of the diamond.

Diamond	(hkl)	Structure	T _m , K	R(I), nm	γ, mJ/m ²	γ, [16] mJ/m ²	γ, [17] mJ/m ²
C	100	Fd3m	4273	0,58 (2)	8546	9100	-
	110				6104	6274	-
	111				5027	5270	4999±355

From the table. 1 It follows that for the diamond, the thickness of the surface layer is 0.58 nm and contains only 2 monolayers, where the relaxation or reconstruction of these layers occurs, leading to the emergence of tense conditions. The value of γ_{HKL} for the planes (100), (110) and (111) is compared with the results of the work [16] and [17]. The calculations are based on the work of Harkins [16], published back in 1942, are carried out theoretically on the basis of the thermodynamics of Gibbs. Assuming the energy of the C-C communication in a diamond equal to 90 kcal/mol, and the energy of the diamond cohesia is equal to doubled surface energy, it received the value of γ_{hkl} , shown in the table. 1. The results of the experimental measurement of the surface energy of the diamond by the Griffith method were carried out in 2017 in [17] along the plane (111) and also represented in table. 1. This experimental value of the surface energy of the diamond is very close to the value of γ_{hkl} we received (Table 1). Theoretical assessments of the surface energy of the diamond for the plane (100) were obtained in many works

(mJ/m²): 9400 [18], 6513 [19].

Lonsdelit (Fig. 3g) is not found in the form of an independent phase (except for meteorites from the cosmos), but only in the ranges with diamond. Therefore, he is not considered by us.

Graphite

The graphite is a thermodynamically stable allotropic modification of carbon-the element of the 4th group of the main subgroup of the 2nd period of the periodic system, serial number 6, the atomic mass of the natural mixture of isotopes 12.0107 g/mol. Theoretical density equal to 2.26 g/cm³ is achieved only in natural graphite. The density of artificial graphite is in the range of 1.65-1.75 g/cm³ [5]. Such a low density of artificial graphite is explained by its porosity. The graphite does not melt, but sublimate at a temperature of about 3650 °C [5]. The crystalline structure of graphite has a hexagonal symmetry and consists of flat layers of carbon atoms located parallel to each other (Fig. 3c). The parameters of graphite are given in table. 2.

Table 2.

Graphite parameters

Graphite	ρ, g/sm ³	T _m , K	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ _a , mJ/m ²	γ _c , mJ/m ²
C	2,26	3970 K	0.90 (3)	2.46 (3)	2779	591
	1,75		1.17 (4)	3.19 (4)		
	1,65		1.24 (5)	3.39 (5)		

From the table. 2 shows, with a graphite density of 1.75 g/cm³ in the longitudinal direction R(I)_a = 1.17 nm, and in the transverse direction R(I)_c = 3.19 nm.

Grafen

Grafen is a two -dimensional allotropic modification of carbon, formed by a layer of carbon atoms with a thickness of one atom (R(I) = a = 0.246 nm - a stalarian grill) that are in a state of sp² - hybridization. The graphene layer is a separate single plane of the volu-

metric graphite crystal [20]. For "advanced experiments with two -dimensional material - graphene" A.K. Gaimu and K.S. Novosyolov was awarded the Nobel Physics Prize for 2010. Carbon atoms in graphene layers are in a three -coordinated state, i.e. Each of them forms covalent ties with three neighbors. As a result, a grid of hexagons is formed, the vertices of which are carbon atoms, carbon-carbon bonds form the appropriate sides. Grafen melting temperature T_m = 4510 K [21]. Grafen's parameters are given in table. 3.

Table 3.

Grafen parameters

Grafen	ρ, g/sm ³	T _m , K	R(I) _a , nm	γ _a , mJ/m ²
C	2,26	4510	0,246	3157

Carbin

Carbynes are a polymeric polyynes (-C≡C-) _m or cumulene (=C=C=) _n chain consisting of carbon atoms in sp-hybridization (Fig. 1a). The polymer chains in carbyne crystals are packed in the form of hexagons along the (001) face. The presence of bends in the chains leads to displacement of the layers.

The hexagonal cell of an α-carbyne crystal has the following crystal lattice parameters: a = b = 0.894 nm

and c = 1.536 nm; for β-carbyne - a = b = 0.824 nm and c = 0.768 nm [6]. The density of carbyne crystals is 1.9-2.0 g/cm³. The melting point is about 3970 K. Using these data, we estimate the thickness of the surface layer and the anisotropy of the surface energy of the carbyne (Table 4) Here R(I)_a = 38.6 nm since the molar mass of carbon in the cell is M = 12x6 = 72, where 6 is six-atom chain [6], ρ ≈ 2.0 g/cm³.

Table 4.

Carbine parameters

Carbin	Structure	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ _a , mJ/m ²	γ _c , mJ/m ²
C	α-carbin	38,6 (43)	196,7 (128)	4257	21692
	β- carbin	30,2 (37)	40,0 (52)	3330	4411

From the table 4 shows that for α-carbyne R(I)_a = 38.6 (43) and R(I)_c = 196.7 (128), which is significantly more than 100 nm. It turned out that carbyne is the strongest of all known materials [6]. The specific strength of a carbine is $6.0 \cdot 10^7 - 7.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, and the specific strength of diamond is $2.5 \cdot 10^7 - 6.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, graphene - $4.7 \cdot 10^7 - 5.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/ kg, carbon nanotubes – $4.3 \cdot 10^7 - 5.0 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg. Carbin is the most durable material. The specific rigidity of carbyne is about 10^9 N m/kg, which is two times higher than the specific rigidity of graphene - $0.45 \cdot 10^9$ N m/kg.

Fullerenes

Fullerene was discovered in 1985 by G. Croto (Great Britain), R. Curl, R. Smellie (USA), for which they were awarded the Nobel Prize in 1996. The substance was named after the American architect and engineer R.B. Fullura, who built the US Pavilion at the

1967 Montreal Exposition using a structure of articulated pentagons and hexagons. A review of fullerenes for 15 years from 1991 to 2006 was carried out in [22]. The most recent monograph on the structure and stability of higher fullerenes is presented in [23]. Fullerenes are carbon clusters with an even, more than 20, number of carbon atoms forming three bonds with each other; the atoms in fullerenes are located on the surface of the spheroid at the vertices of hexagons and pentagons (Fig. 3e, f).

At the moment, the most common and studied fullerenes are C₆₀ and C₇₀. Fullerenes with more than 70 atoms (for example, C₇₆, C₇₈, C₈₄, C₉₆) are called higher fullerenes. The parameters of fullerenes are presented in table. 5.

Table 5.

Fullerene parameters.

Fullerene	T _m , K	M, g/mol	ρ, g/sm ³	R(I), nm	γ, mJ/m ²
C ₃₆	1404	432,40	1,810	40,61 (36)	1404
C ₆₀	2031	720,66	1,484	85,56 (60)	2031
C ₇₀	2260	840,23	1,547	93,39 (64)	2260
C ₇₆	2387	912,84	1,582	98,09	2367
C ₈₄	2547	1008,92	1,589	107,93	2547
C ₉₆	2763	1154,06	1,452	135,0	2763

For fullerenes, for C₆₀ R(I) = 85.6 (60) nm, for C₇₀ R(I) = 93.4 (64).

Amorphous carbon

Amorphous carbon (Fig. 3f) is also called carbon black or soot. Carbon black particles are globules consisting of degraded graphite structures [1-4]. The distance between the graphite-like layers is 0.35-0.365 nm (in graphite 0.335 nm - Fig. 3c). On average: melting point T_m = 3820 K, density ρ = 1.7 g/cm³. The parameters of amorphous carbon are shown in table. 6.

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Table 6.

Parameters of amorphous carbon.

Amorphous carbon	ρ, g/sm ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ _a , mJ/m ²	γ _c , mJ/m ²
C	1,7	1,20 (3)	3,28 (3)	2674	569

The basis of carbon nanotubes is a graphene plane conventionally rolled into a cylinder, composed of regular hexagons, the nodes of which are carbon atoms in the state of sp² hybridization (Fig. 3i, k) [24]. Unlike a flat graphene sheet, in carbon nanotubes the overall p-electron cloud is deformed, compressed inside the tube and, on the contrary, stretched along the outer surface. The smaller the diameter of the nanotube, the greater the degree of deformation. This is reflected in the strength of the bonds: the greater the curvature of the nanotube surface, the less the degree of overlap of p-orbitals, and the higher the chemical reactivity of the nanotube. Graphene parameters from table 3 also applies well to carbon nanotubes, so we will not consider them in detail.

Peierls–Nabarro barrier

We compare the R(I) monolayer with the Peierls–Nabarro barrier, which is equal to the force of interatomic interaction [25, 26]. In contrast to the Frenkel–

Kontorova model [27], as well as works [28, 29] and others, we will propose a model that can be used to estimate the barrier F(I)_{P-N} and the Peierls – Nabarro voltage σ(I)_{P-N}:

$$F(I)_{P-N} = \gamma_1 \cdot R(I)/n = \gamma_1 \cdot a, \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma(I)_{P-N} = F(I)/S = \gamma_1/a = E \cdot \varepsilon(I),$$

where γ₁ ≈ 0.3 γ; n – number of layers in layer R(I); a is the lattice constant; S – barrier area (a²), σ(I)_{P-N}, – Peierls–Nabarro stress; E – Young's modulus; ε represents the relative elongation of the lattice parameter in the direction of the external force F.

Relation (7) shows that the Peierls–Nabarro barrier in the R(I) layer is completely determined by experimentally determined values and is presented in Table. 7.

Table 7.

Barrier F(I) and Peierls–Nabarro stresses $\sigma(I)$ of carbon materials

Carbon	Structure	$F(I)_{aP-N}$, 10^{-9} N	$F(I)_{cP-N}$, 10^{-9} N	$\sigma(I)_{aP-N}$, MPa	$\sigma(I)_{cP-N}$, MPa
Diamond	Fd3m	1,02	-	7983	-
Graphite	$P6_3/mmc$	0,23	0,13	3783	294
Grafen	hexagon	0,26	-	4268	-
Carbin	α - carbin	1,29	11,2	1587	4707
	β - carbin	0,91	0,88	1347	1484
Fullerene					
C_{36}	Fd3m	0,55	-	399	-
C_{60}	Fd3m	0,96	-	478	-
C_{70}	Fd3m	1,13	-	503	-
Amorphous carbon	aC	0,33	0,07	2441	191

You can add the term $\sin(2\pi z/a)$ to equation (7) and show the relief of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier [25–29]. In [30], we compared the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ to the length of nanocracks L_{nm} , which appears in any solid during the formation of its surface. In this case, the surface layer $R(I)$ is subjected to internal stresses due to relaxation or reconstruction of the surface. These stresses cause the formation of edge and screw dislocations, which interact with each other, leading to the formation of nanocracks. Nanocracks were experimentally discovered recently [31]. The nanocrack grows according to the law: $L_{nm} \rightarrow L_{\mu m} = 10^2 \cdot L_{nm} \rightarrow L_C = 10^4 \cdot L_{nm}$. For diamond $L_{nm} = 0.58 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m, then $L_C = 0.58 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m = 5.8 microns.

From the table 7 it follows that the height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier is maximum: carbine $\rightarrow C_{70} \rightarrow$ diamond. If we want to increase the strength and strengthen the material, then we need to increase the

height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier for moving dislocations (nanocracks) in the crystal structure [32].

Let's consider carbon materials, starting with diamond, which has a very small thickness of the $R(I)$ layer and only 2 monolayers, where surface reconstruction occurs and stressed states arise. The bonding of atoms on the surface of the diamond lattice cannot be tetrahedral, and the most likely possibility is that the atoms are held by three normal bonds, and the remaining unpaired orbits form defect bonds, which also leads to the formation of additional energy levels inside the band gap [33]. Another factor causing lattice periodicity violations are dislocations - displacements of atomic planes that arise as a result of mechanical stresses during the growth of a diamond crystal. Under the influence of dislocations, some bonds may be deformed and some may be broken, which ultimately leads to the formation of new energy levels inside the band gap (Fig. 5a) [33].

Figure 5. Diagram of the band structure of diamond, taking into account energy levels caused by lattice defects (a) [33]; fragment of an X-ray topogram of diamond plastically deformed by the dislocation sliding mechanism, reflection (220), the diffraction vector is directed horizontally to the right, area size 0.8x1.2 mm (b) [34].

In Fig. 5a width: valence band $\Delta E_B \approx 20$ eV, band gap for indirect transitions $\Delta E_{OH} = 5.47$ eV, band gap for direct transitions $\Delta E_{OII} = 7.3$ eV, $\Delta E'$ - band gap between the first four and subsequent levels of the conduction band. An ideal crystal of infinite extent should

not contain energy levels between the upper boundary of the valence band I, which is completely filled, and the bottom of the completely empty conduction band II, with the exception of empty exciton levels III located near the intrinsic absorption edge.

In a real crystal, energy levels appear inside the band gap, indicated in Fig. 5a with dashed lines, responsible for which are lattice defects. Dislocations are responsible for energy levels 1, located near the top of the valence band, and energy levels 2, located very close to the bottom of the conduction band. Isolated vacancies are responsible for energy levels 3, located slightly above levels 1, but still quite close to the upper boundary of the valence band. As the number of vacancies increases, new levels 4 appear, approaching the middle of the bandgap. The presence of intermediate carbon atoms in interstices does not significantly change the pattern of energy level distribution inside the band gap, except for an increase in the number of levels in the vicinity of 1 and 3. Finally, levels 5, located approximately in the middle of the band gap, are due to the surface effect. According to [33], the energy levels discussed above, caused by lattice defects, are normally filled.

The main role in natural diamond crystals, both in abundance and concentration, is played by three nitrogen centers - P_1 , P_2 and N_2 . The N_2 center is considered as a manifestation of deformation dislocations with free bonds in the core [34]. Crystals plastically deformed by

the dislocation sliding mechanism are the most widespread among natural diamonds. X-ray topograms [34] (Fig. 5b) show that gliding deformation dislocations are very unevenly distributed throughout the crystal volume. The formation of curvilinear dislocations is associated with elevated deformation temperatures, significantly higher than the temperature at which diamond transitions from a brittle to a plastic state (about 1200 °C) [34]. The centers for the formation of deformation dislocations were localized defective areas, which were microinclusions or microcracks, as well as Frank-Reed sources [34]. The development of plastic deformation of natural diamonds according to the mechanism of mechanical twinning was established in pink-violet diamonds based on an analysis of their ESR spectra. In these diamonds, deformation lamellae with characteristic mirror reflections from the boundaries were also observed, which is a sign of microtwins (Fig. 6a) [34].

Theoretical consideration and modeling showed that the hexagonal diffraction pattern is actually the result of the superposition of two diffraction patterns of cubic symmetry, which are in a twinning position according to the spinel law with the $\{111\}$ twinning plane (Fig. 6b) [34]. These data clearly prove the presence of deformation microtwins in diamonds.

Figure 6. A plate (4x4 mm) made of natural diamond with deformation microtwins, in reflected light (a) and the diffraction pattern of this diamond with domains A and B located in the twin position (b) [34].

Let us now turn to graphite. In layered crystal structures, due to the strong anisotropy of interatomic bonds, defects and their complexes have a shape flattened along the basal planes. This leads to heterogeneity and special distributions of microstrain values in real crystal structures [35].

From the table 7 it follows that the height of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier of graphite is 5 times less than that of diamond. In [36, 37] Indenbom V.L. obtained for ionic crystals an average value of $F(I) = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, which is close to graphite $F(I)_{aP-N} = 0.23 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N and $F(I)_{cP-N} = 0.13 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N. Defects in graphite according to [5] can be divided into two types: defects related to violations between layers, and bond defects in networks. The first include layer packing defects, characterized by a violation of the packing order of parallel layers of hexagonal networks. The second type of structural damage in graphite is defects in the bonds of the carbon lattice. These include vacancies and their groups, impurity atoms embedded in the hexagonal layer, defects in

isomeric bonds when some of the atoms have sp^3 hybridization, edge defects, etc.

In graphene, the deformation of the quasi-two-dimensional lattice created by defects can induce strong pseudomagnetic fields, promote the appearance of new Landau levels, paramagnetic centers, etc., which has a significant impact on the electronic characteristics. In [38], the formation and movement of dislocations in graphene was studied in real time using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy. It was established in [38] that the source of dislocations in graphene are the so-called Stone-Wales defects (SW), which are formed as a result of rotation of the C–C bond through an angle of 90° , as a result of which two 5-gons and two 7-gons appear in the hexagonal lattice. Square dislocations move by sliding or crawling at a speed of ~ 0.1 nm/min. Each dislocation creates a deformation field in its vicinity, which extends over ~ 1 nm.

Figure 7. (A) Stone-Wales defect in graphene. (B) Dislocations in graphene. Thin arrows are Burgers vectors. Thick arrows show the directions of displacement of atoms when a dislocation glides to the right. (C) Atomic configuration resulting from sliding. If an electron beam knocks out two labeled atoms, then the dislocation creeps down. (D) Atomic configuration after crawling.

From the table 7 it follows that the Peierls–Nabarro stress $\sigma(I) = 4.3$ GPa, which leads to warping of graphene [39]. Also, the Stone-Wales defect can be considered as a dislocation dipole, in which two edge dislocations with opposite signs of the Burgers vector are shifted by one lattice period [39].

Peierls-Nabarro barrier $F(I) = 1.29 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N for α -carbyne (Table 7), which is greater than that of diamond. This means dislocation inhibition for α -carbyne and means its strength. The specific strength of a carbyne is $6.0 \cdot 10^7 - 7.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg, and the specific strength of a diamond is $2.5 \cdot 10^7 - 6.5 \cdot 10^7$ N m/kg.

The Peierls-Nabarro barrier $F(I) = 1.13 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N for C_{70} fullerene (Table 7), which is greater than that of diamond. Today, there are several mechanisms of dislocation braking, which can be divided into two groups.

The first group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence in crystals of potential barriers caused by various structural defects (impurities, etc.), including the Peierls-Nabarro barrier, which for steels $F(I)_{P-N} \approx 0.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, which greater than that of graphite, graphene and amorphous carbon. The second group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence of dynamic interaction in crystals. This includes interaction with electrons, phonons, excitons, magnons and other elementary excitations of the crystal lattice. The role of the latter excitations for most crystals is insignificant, but the interaction with phonons is most significant.

We will apply our model (7) and estimate the barrier $F(I)_{P-N}$ and Peierls–Nabarro stresses $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$ for iron oxides (Table 8).

Table 8.

Surface energy of the layer $R(I) - \gamma_1$, barrier $F(I)_{P-N}$ and Peierls–Nabarro stress $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$, ε - relative elongation of the lattice parameter.

Oxide	(hkl)	$\gamma_1, \text{J/m}^2$	$F(I)_{P-N}, 10^{-9} \text{ N}$	$\sigma(I)_{P-N}, \text{MPa}$	ε
Fe_2O_3	(100)	0.260	0.217	374.7	0.002
	(110)	0.371	0.309	445.3	0.002
	(111)	0.612	0.510	734.9	0.003
Fe_3O_4	(100)	0.243	0.204	242.6	0.001
	(110)	0.346	0.291	412.4	0.002
	(111)	0.571	0.480	680.3	0.003
FeO	(100)	0.428	0.182	1009	0.006
	(110)	0.306	0.130	721.1	0.004
	(111)	0.504	0.214	1187	0.007

Comparison of table 7 and 8 shows that, in addition to carbyne, C_{70} fullerene and diamond, most crystals, including steels, have Peierls-Nabarro barriers that do not exceed $1 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N, so they are not as strong as diamond.

Conclusion

If we want to increase strength and strengthen the material, then we need to increase the number of barriers to moving dislocations in the crystal structure:

1. Peierls-Nabarro barrier - the force of interatomic interaction.
2. Inhibition of dislocations by grain and subgrain boundaries.

3. Inhibition of dislocations, when distortions of the crystal lattice are caused by the presence of impurity atoms.

4. Inhibition of dislocations by segregations of interstitial impurity atoms (Cottrell atmosphere).

5. Braking of dislocations by other dislocations.

6. Inhibition of dislocations by dispersed precipitation particles.

7. Inhibition of dislocations by Guinier-Preston zones.

8. Braking of dislocations by electrons in metals.

9. Braking of dislocations by phonons in crystals.

10. Inhibition of dislocations by elementary excitations (magnons, excitons, etc.) in solids.

Here we considered the Peierls-Nabarro barrier and proposed a model for its evaluation for the surface layer of carbon materials, where the destruction of the material begins.

This scientific article was published as part of grant funding for 2024-2026, IRN No. AR32488258 "Development of innovative technology for producing graphene by intercalating graphite with microcluster water and modifying HTSC ceramics with graphene" (the research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan).

References:

1. Belenkov E.A., Ivanovskaya V.V., Ivanovsky A.L. Nanodiamonds and related carbon materials. - Ekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2008. - 166 p.
2. Shumilova T.G. Mineralogy of native carbon. - Ekaterinburg: Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2003. - 315 p.
3. Kurdyumov A.V., Pilyankevich A.N. Phase transformations in carbon and boron nitride. - Kyiv: Naukova Dumka, 1979. - 188 p.
4. Kurdyumov A.V., Malogolovets V.G., Novikov N.V. and others. Polymorphic modifications of carbon and boron nitride. - M.: Metallurgy, 1994. - 318 p.
5. Zhmurikov E.I., Bubnenkov I.A., Dremov V.V., Samarin S.I., Pokrovsky A.S., Kharkov D.V. Graphite in science and nuclear technology. - Novosibirsk, 2013. - 193 p.
6. Belenkov E.A., Mavrinsky V.V. Crystal structure of ideal carbyne // Crystallography, 2008, V. 53, No. 1. - P.83-87.
7. Heimann R.B., Evsyukov S.E., Koga Y. Carbon allotropes: a suggested classification scheme based on valence orbital hybridization // Carbon, 1997, V.35, №10-11. - P. 1654-1663.
8. Bundy F.P., Bassett W.A., et al. The Pressure-Temperature Phase and Transformation Diagram for Carbon; Updated Through 1994 // Carbon, 1996, V. 34, N 2. - P. 141-153.
9. Gan Y. X., Jang B. Z. A parametric derivation method for solving the Peierls - Nabarro dislocation equation with a non-sinusoidal law of interatomic forces // J. Mater. Sci. Lett., 1996, V. 15. - P. 2044-2047.
10. Vitek V. Intrinsic stacking faults in body-centered cubic crystals // Philos. Mag., 1968, V. 18. - P. 773-786.
11. Yurov V.M., Guchenko S.A., Laurynas V.Ch. Surface layer thickness, surface energy and atomic volume of an element // Physico-chemical aspects of the study of clusters, nanostructures and nanomaterials, 2018, Vol. 10. - P. 691-699.
12. Tolman R.C. The effect of droplet size on surface tension // J. Chem. Phys., 1949, Vol. 17, № 2. - P. 333-337.
13. Rekhviashvili S.Sh., Kishtikova E.V., Karmokova R.Yu. On the calculation of the Tolman constant // Letters to ZhTP, 2007, V. 33, no. 2. - P. 1-7.
14. Bokarev V.P., Krasnikov G.Ya. Anisotropy of physical and chemical properties of single-crystal surfaces // Electronic technology. Series 3. Microelectronics, 2016, No.4 (164). - P. 25-30.
15. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S. Anisotropy of the surface of cubic body-centered crystal lattices // Eurasian Physical Technical Journal, 2021, Vol.18, No. 1(35). - P. 9-15.
16. Harkins W. D. Energy Relations of surface of Solids // Journal Chem. Phys., 1942, V. 10. - P. 268-272.
17. Nozhkina A.V., Kostikov V.I. Surface energy of diamond and graphite // Rock-cutting and metal-working tools - technique and technology of its manufacture and application, 2017, No. 20. - P. 161-167.
18. Ormont B.F. Introduction to physical chemistry and crystal chemistry of semiconductors. - M.: Nauka, 1982. - 487 p.
19. Oshcherin B.N. On surface energies of ANB8-N semiconducting compounds. Phys. Status Solidi, 1976, A 34, No. 2. - P. K 181-K186.
20. Novoselov K. S. Graphene: materials of Flatland // UFN, 2011, V. 181, No. 12. - P. 1299-1311.
21. Los J.H., Zakharchenko K.V., Katsnelson M.I. and Fasolino A. Melting temperature of graphene // Phys. Rev., 2015, B91, 045415.
22. Zeynalov E.B. Fullerenes: Information collection (1991-2006). Baku: "Nurlan", 2007.-521 p.
23. Kovalenko V.I., Khamatgalimov A.R. Structure and stability of higher fullerenes. - M.: RAS, 2019. - 212 p.
24. Eletsky A.V. Carbon nanotubes and their emission properties. // UFN, 2002, V. 172, No. 4. - P. 401-438.
25. Peierls R. The size of a dislocation // Proc. Phys. Soc. London, 1940, V. 52. - P. 34-37.
26. Nabarro F.R.N. Dislocations in a simple cubic lattice // Proc. Phys. Soc. London, 1947, V. 59. - P. 256-272.
27. Usatenko O.V., Gorbach A.V., Kovalev A.S. Energy and Peierls barrier of the Frenkel-Kontorova dislocation (kink) // FTT, 2001, vol. 43, issue. 7. - P. 1202-1206.
28. Grinberg B.A., Ivanov M.A., Kruglikov N.A., Antonova O.V. On the possibility of self-blocking of dislocations in various materials // Physics and Mathematics, 2009, V. 108, No.1. - P. 93-104.
29. Fan T., Luo L., Ma L., Tang B., Peng L., Ding W. Study of total a-dislocations in pure magnesium based on first principles // PMT, 2014, V. 55, N4. - P. 141-151.
30. Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S. Study of primary nanocracks in atomically smooth metals // Letters to ZhTP, 2023, vol. 49, issue. 8. P. 35-38.
31. Vettegren V.I., Ponomarev A.V., Mamalimov R.I., Shcherbakov I.P. Nanocracks during the destruction of oligoclase // Physics of the Earth, 2021, No. 6. - P. 87-92.

32. Petukhov B.V. Dynamics of dislocations in solid solutions of covalent crystals // FTT, 2016, vol. 58, issue. 9. – P. 1764-1768.

33. Wuberman G.S. Zone structure of diamonds // UFN, 1971, V. 103, No. 4. – P. 675-704.

34. Titkov S.V. Isomorphic impurities in natural diamonds and their genetic significance. – Abstract of Doctor of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences, Moscow, 2018. – 38 p.

35. Isaev E.I. Radiation changes in the real structure of layered materials using the example of graphite and graphite-like boron nitride. – Abstract of the candidate in Physics and Mathematics. Sciences, Moscow, 2018. – 20 p.

36. Indenbom V.L., Orlov L.Zh. Physical theory of plasticity and strength // UFN, 1962, V. LXXVI, issue 3. – P. 558-591.

37. Alshits V.I., Indenbom V.L. Dynamic braking of dislocations // UFN, 1975, Vol. 115, no. 1. – P. 3-39.

38. Warner J.H., Margine E.R., Mukai M., Robertson A.W., Giustino F., Kirkland A.I. Dislocation-driven deformations in grapheme // Science, 2012, Vol. 337. - P. 209-212.

39. Akhunova A.Kh., Baimova Yu.A. The influence of dislocation dipoles with different arms on the deformation behavior of graphene: molecular dynamics // ZhTP, 2023, vol. 93, no. 4. – P. 445-452.